

Fibroblast Growth Factor-23 importance as a prognostic factor in Hemodialysis Patients

Importancia del factor de crecimiento de fibroblastos-23 como factor pronóstico en pacientes en hemodiálisis

Mohammed Younus Naji Al Atbee^{1*}, Ali Hussein Hamu², Faten Abdulghani Hammoudi³, Ali Abdulmajid Dyab Allawi⁴, Hala Sami Tuama⁵

¹Consultant Nephrologist, Assistant Professor, College of Medicine, University of Basrah, Iraq. ORCID id: 0000-0002-8568-1567. Email: mohammed.naji@uobasrah.edu.iq

²Nephrologist and Internist, Baquba teaching Hospital, Iraq. ORCID id: 0009-0006-6246-4769. email: drali.hamu@gmail.com

³Specialist in Laboratory Diagnosis, Baghdad Medical City, Iraq. ORCID id: 0000-0002-8663-0200. email: faten.all.lab@gmail.com

⁴Professor, Consultant Nephrologist and Internist, Baghdad Medical College, Iraq. ORCID id: 0000-0002-1282-1813. Email: aliallawi@comed.uobaghdad.edu.iq

⁵Family Physician, Al Mohandessin Primary Health Care, Basrah, Iraq. ORCID id: 0000-0002-7545-538X. Email: halasamifamily@gmail.com

Corresponding author: Mohammed Younus Naji Al Atbee, Department of Nephrology, College of Medicine, University of Basrah, Basrah, Iraq, Tel Number: 009647702757827, 00964781489400, Email: Mohammed.naji@uobasrah.edu.iq, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8568-1567>

Received: 04/20/2022 Accepted: 06/19/2023 Published: 08/25/2023 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8365155>

232

Abstract

Background: Initial complication evident in chronic kidney disease (CKD) are enhanced levels of Fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23) along with phosphate homeostasis disorders. Increase in amount of FGF23 is a highly sensitive indicator of phosphate toxicity and end-organ toxicity in the heart.

Objective: The objective of the current research was exploring the correlation between the quantity of FGF23 and bone-mineral metabolism, anemia and left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) and dysfunction (LVEF).

Methods: This research was executed at the nephrology units, dialysis department / Baghdad teaching hospital and basrah teaching hospital during 1st of January 2021 to 1 of March 2022. 60 patients undergoing hemodialysis for minimum of six months were recruited in the research. Parameters assessed included hematocrit (Htc), hemoglobin (Hb), phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), corrected albumin, whole parathyroid hormone (iPTH). We further calculated if any correlation existed between these parameters and FGF23 levels. We also conducted left ventricular echocardiography of the recruited patients

to evaluate the relation between FGF23, LVH and LVEF.

Results: We found statistically significant positive correlation between serum FGF23 levels and iPTH (P < 0.001), Ca values (P < 0.001). However, we were unable to find a substantial correlation between the levels of FGF23 and Hb (P = 0.518) and Htc (P = 0.377). FGF23 and LVH were also statistically correlated (P < 0.001).

Significant negative correlation of FGF23 was found with LVEF showing a decrease in LVEF with increasing levels of FGF23 (P < 0.001).

Conclusion: Elevated serum FGF-23 levels in hemodialysis patients showed significant correlation with various studied parameters indicating its role in development of hyperparathyroidism. Noticeably, our data showed a positive correlation between FGF23 and LVH and negative correlation between FGF23 and LVEF suggesting that FGF23 is sufficient to forecast of overall death rate in patients suffering from CKD.

Keywords: C-reactive protein, parathyroid hormone, Fibroblast growth factor-23, Hemodialysis patients

Resumen

Fondo: La complicación inicial evidente en la enfermedad renal crónica (ERC) son los niveles elevados del factor de crecimiento de fibroblastos 23 (FGF23) junto con los trastornos de la homeostasis del fosfato. El aumento de la cantidad de FGF23 es un indicador muy sensible de la toxicidad del fosfato y de la toxicidad de los órganos terminales en el corazón.

Objetivo: El objetivo de la presente investigación fue explorar la correlación entre la cantidad de FGF23 y el metabolismo mineral óseo, la anemia y la hipertrofia y disfunción del ventrículo izquierdo (HVI) (FEVI).

Métodos: Esta investigación se llevó a cabo en las unidades de nefrología, el departamento de diálisis / hos-

pital universitario de Bagdad y el hospital universitario de Basora durante el 1 de enero de 2021 al 1 de marzo de 2022. En la investigación se reclutaron 60 pacientes sometidos a hemodiálisis durante un mínimo de seis meses. Los parámetros evaluados incluyeron hematocrito (Htc), hemoglobina (Hb), fósforo (P), calcio (Ca), albúmina corregida y hormona paratiroidea total (PTHt). Además, calculamos si existía alguna correlación entre estos parámetros y los niveles de FGF23. También realizamos una ecocardiografía del ventrículo izquierdo de los pacientes reclutados para evaluar la relación entre FGF23, HVI y FEVI.

Resultados: Encontramos una correlación positiva estadísticamente significativa entre los niveles séri-

cos de FGF23 y los valores de PTHi ($P < 0,001$) y Ca ($P < 0,001$). Sin embargo, no pudimos encontrar una correlación sustancial entre los niveles de FGF23 y Hb ($P = 0,518$) y Htc ($P = 0,377$). FGF23 y LVH también se correlacionaron estadísticamente ($P < 0,001$). Se encontró una correlación negativa significativa de FGF23 con la FEVI que muestra una disminución de la FEVI con niveles crecientes de FGF23 ($P < 0,001$).

Conclusión: Los niveles séricos elevados de FGF-23 en pacientes en hemodiálisis mostraron una correlación significativa con varios parámetros estudiados que indican su papel en el desarrollo del hiperparatiroidismo. Notablemente, nuestros datos mostraron una correlación positiva entre FGF23 y HVI y una correlación negativa entre FGF23 y FEVI, lo que sugiere que FGF23 es suficiente para pronosticar la tasa de mortalidad general en pacientes que padecen ERC.

Palabras clave: Proteína C reactiva, hormona paratiroidea, factor de crecimiento de fibroblastos-23, pacientes en hemodiálisis.

Albuminuria should be quantified using urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio. Staging of CKD based on albuminuria has been classified as⁵:

1. A1: urine ACR < 30 mg/g
2. A2: urine 30–300 mg/g
3. A3: urine > 300 mg/g

Study setting and design:

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the nephrology units, dialysis department of Baghdad teaching hospital and basrah teaching hospital during 1st of January 2021 to 1 of march 2022. This study recruited 60 patients: 34 males and 26 females. The included patient's age ranged between 25-70 years. All the recruited patients for this study were receiving hemodialysis replacement therapy minimum for last six months. Patients having chronic and active inflammatory disease (e.g., collagen tissue disease, malignancy, and diabetic foot) and incompliant patients were excluded from our study. Based on the serum level of PTH level less or more than 300 pg/mL, recruited patients were divided into two groups. Group A and Group B respectively⁶.

Blood samples were collected from all the patients' post overnight fasting. Parameters studied included serum albumin, hematocrit (Htc), hemoglobin (Hb), calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), intact PTH (iPTH), and FGF-23 levels. Calculation of $CaxP$ ratio was also done for each patient.

To evaluate the hemodialysis adequacy, Kt/V values were calculated for each patient using hemodialysis machine.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) Statistical Software was used in this study for all the data analysis. We used one-way variance analysis for descriptive statistical methods viz. mean, standard deviation, median, and interquartile range. For conformity of variables to a normal distribution, logarithmic transformation was applied for FGF-23 and for PTH, square root transformation was applied. For comparison of two groups, independent t-test was used and for comparison of the variables with non-normal distribution, we used Mann-Whitney test. Qualitative data comparison was performed using Chi-square test. For defining the parameters which affect FGF 23, linear regression analysis was carried out. < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Chronic kidney disease

The health condition, chronic kidney disease (CKD), affects nearly 8-16% of the population worldwide¹. It is defined by the occurrence of structural and functional abnormality of the kidney that is evident for more than 3 months of time duration. These abnormalities include glomerular filtration rate below 60 mL/min/1.73 m², albuminuria, abnormalities in histology, urine sediment, or kidney damage evident by imaging, disorders in renal tubules, or history of kidney transplantation². Prevalence of CKD has been found to be more in lower and middle countries as compared to high income countries³. Major contributing factors for CKD include diabetes and/or hypertension, however other causes like infection, environmental exposure and glomerulonephritis are also attribute to the development of CKD in Asian, African⁴. Various genetic factors have also been found to have a role in the development of CKD^{5,6}.

Staging based on GFR is classified as⁵:

Grade 1 – GFR > 90 mL/min per 1.73 m²

Grade 2 – GFR 60 to 89 mL/min per 1.73 m²

Grade 3a – GFR 45 to 59 mL/min per 1.73 m²

Grade 3b – GFR 30 to 44 mL/min per 1.73 m²

Grade 4 – GFR 15 to 29 mL/min per 1.73 m²

Grade 5 – GFR < 15 mL/min per 1.73 m² or treatment by dialysis

We had recruited 60 patients who were followed up at nephrology unit, dialysis department of Baghdad teaching hospital and were undergoing dialysis replacement therapy for at least 6 months. These patients were divided into two study groups based on the serum PTH levels as mentioned above viz. Group A with PTH level below 300 pg/mL and Group B with serum PTH level above 300 pg/mL.

Demographic data:

The mean age of all the recruited patients was 50.43 ± 12 . Mean age individually of the patients recruited for the study in the Group A was 49.03 ± 11.52 and in the Group B was 51.84 ± 12 . Of all the patients recruited, 20 were male (57.1%) and 15 females (42.9%) in Group A and 14 males (56%) and 11 females (44%) in Group B. There was no significant difference between the mean age and gender distribution of the patients between both the groups (Table 1).

	iPTH <300	iPTH $\geq$ 300	All	P value
Number of Patients(%)	35(58.3)	25(42.7)	60	-
Age years (Mean $\pm$ SD)	49.03 $\pm$ 11.52	51.84 $\pm$ 12.7	50.43 $\pm$ 12	0.376
Gender: Male(%)	20 (57.1)	14 (56)	34 (56.7)	0.93
Female(%)	15 (42.9)	11 (44)	26 (43.3)	0.75

T test, chi square was used

Biochemical parameters:

Serum Biochemistry:

Serum biochemistries for the total cohort ($n = 60$) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 biochemical profile of the study group.

	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Hemoglobin	8.21	1.5	4.90	12.90
Hct	26.05	4.71	14.90	41.90
Calcium	6.75	1.44	3.30	12.20
PO ₄	5.95	1.7	3.00	13.40
Ca x PO ₄ ^a	35.76	30.28 – 45.13		
iPTH ^a	232.9	133 – 903.8	40.25	1014
FGF-23 ^a	334.5	260.8 - 1500	188	1500
Vitamin D ₃ ^a	161.4	105.4 – 355.2	39.3	557
Albumin ^a	3.5	2.9 – 4.07	1.2	5.2
Kt/V ^a	0.95	0.7 – 1.3	0.95	1.96

^aData presented using median and interquartile range

As mentioned above, depending on the parathyroid hormone level dialysis patients were divided into two groups viz. Group A (iPTH <300) and Group B (iPTH $\geq$ 300). Biochemical parameters viz. Hemoglobin, hematocrit, Vitamin D₃, and Kt/V although had higher values in group B in comparison to group A but did not show any difference when compared between both the groups (P value > 0.05). Serum levels of calcium ($p=0.007$), phosphate ($p<0.001$), calcium phosphate product ($p=0.043$), FGF-23 ($p<0.001$) and albumin ($p=0.01$) were found to be significantly higher in group A when compared with group B (Table 3).

Table 3: Biochemical data of patients divided by iPTH

Normal distribution	PTH <300		PTH $\geq$ 300		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Number	35		25		-
Hemoglobin	8.32	1.72	8.06	1.15	0.518
Hct	26.51	5.46	25.41	3.41	0.377
Calcium	6.38	1.05	7.34	1.6	0.007
PO ₄	5.1	0.78	7.22	1.79	<0.001
Non normal distribution	Median	IQR	Median	IQR	
Ca x PO ₄ product ^a	35.19	29.58 – 39.33	42	30.55 – 54.03	0.043
FGF-23 ^a	271.57	235.5 – 328.4	1500	1138.5 – 1500	<0.001
Vitamin D ₃ ^a	157.3	116.2 – 469.8	197.7	85.5 – 430.3	0.793
Albumin ^a	3.1	2.9 – 3.8	3.9	3.3 – 4.25	0.01
Kt/V ^a	0.93	0.7 – 1.24	0.99	0.79 – 1.34	0.525

^a: median and IQR (interquartile range) used

t test for normally distributed variables, and Mann Whitney U test for non-normal distribution variables

Results of univariate analysis showed a statistically significant positive correlation between FGF23 values and iPTH values at a level of 78.2% ($r^2: 0.612, p<.001$). FGF23 and Ca also showed positive statistically significant correlation ($r^2: 0.222, p<.001$). We found a positive and statistically significant correlation between FGF23 and between FGF-23 values and PO₄ at a level of 28.1% ($r^2: 0.366, p<.001$) (table 4 and figure 3, 4 and 5).

Table 4: univariate Pearson correlation of Log₁₀ FGF-23 and various variable

Variables	Standardized beta	R ²	P value
iPTH	0.782	0.612	<0.001
Ca	0.471	0.222	<0.001
PO ₄	0.605	0.366	<0.001
Ca x PO ₄ product	0.247	0.061	0.058
Albumin	0.064	0.004	0.629
Vitamin D ₃	0.037	0.001	0.781
Kt/V	-0.088	0.008	0.575

R²: coefficient of determination, standardized beta: correlation coefficient

No significant correlation was found between FGF-23 and Hb and Hct as illustrated in table 5.

Table 5: univariate Pearson correlation of Log₁₀ FGF-23 and various variable

Variables	Standardized beta	R ²	P value
Hb	-0.154	0.024	0.239
Hct	-0.111	0.012	0.399

R²: coefficient of determination, standardized beta: correlation coefficient

In multivariate analysis, it was observed that iPTH and Log₁₀ FGF-23 and PO₄ were positively correlated. This correlation remained significant after the adjustment to the effect of other variables in module (iPTH, Ca, calcium phosphate product, age, albumin, vitamin D₃ and Kt/V) meaning iPTH and PO₄ are independently correlated with Log₁₀ FGF-23 (Table 6). It was calculated that the effect of iPTH was significant at the level of p=0.000. The effect of PO₄ was also found to be significant at the level of p=0.018 (Table 6). However, the correlation between Ca and FGF23 became insignificant with the effect of other variables (Table 6).

Table 6: multivariable correlation of Log₁₀ FGF-23 and various variable

Variables	Standardized beta	P value
Constant	-	0.000
iPTH	0.591	0.000
Ca	0.195	0.157
PO ₄	0.338	0.018
Ca x PO ₄ product	-0.222	0.134
Albumin	-0.029	0.776
Vitamin D ₃	0.080	0.436
Kt/V	0.086	0.426

FGF23, LVH and Ejection function:

FGF23 was found to have a statistically significant positive correlation with interventricular sep-tum end diastolic diameter (IVSd)/left ventricular posterior wall end diastolic diameter (LVPWd) (r: 0.428, p=.001). We found a statistically significant negative correlation between FGF23 levels and ejection fraction (r:-0.458, p<0.001) (Table 7, figure 1 and 2).

Table 7: correlation between FGF and EF and LVH

	r	R ²	P value
EF	-0.458	0.210	<0.001
IVsd/PWd	0.428	0.184	0.001

Figure 6: scatter plot of FGF23 level and Ejection fraction

Figure 7: scatter plot of FGF23 level and Left ventricular hypertrophy

Discussion

Fibroblast growth factor-23 has an important role in mineral metabolism, metabolism of vitamin D, functions of parathyroid glands and excretion of phosphate from the kidney. It has been found that serum levels of FGF23 start increasing as soon as glomerular filtration rate falls below 90 mL/min/ per 1,73 square meters. Considering this, it has been thought that FGF23 could act as a prognostic marker which increases parallel with PO₄ levels from the early stages of CKD and contributes to the development of secondary hyperparathyroidism by suppressing levels of 1,25(OH)₂D and increasing the excretion of PO₄(7). Keeping this in view, in the present study In this study, we aimed to establish a correlation between FGF23 and parameters such as serum PO₄, iPTH, Ca which affect the rate of mortality and morbidity in the CKD patients undergoing dialysis.

60 patients were recruited for this study and these patients were divided in two groups based on the serum concentration of iPTH (Group A and Group B). Demographic data showed no significant difference between the recruited patients based on the age and gender in both the groups. The comparison was done between both the groups for various biochemical parameters. We did not find any significant difference between the values of hemoglobin, hematocrit, Vitamin D₃, and albumin. Noticeably, the levels of Ca, PO₄ and FGF23 were found to be significantly high in group with high level of iPTH. Studies have shown that levels of FGF23 in serum increase prior to the increase in PTH in CKD⁸. As abovesaid, FGF23 contribute to the development of secondary hyperparathyroidism by suppressing levels of vitamin D, excretion of phosphorus²⁹. Moreover, inhibition of enzyme 1-alpha-hydroxylase with increased

production of FGF23 also leads to decreased calcium absorption in intestine leading to increase in PTH level. Our study data was in line with these findings as we observed high levels of FGF23 in group A with high level of PTH⁹. We also observed the increased levels of PO₄ in patients with high levels of PTH. Various studies have shown that increased level of PO₄ is related to increased PTH levels in CKD. It has been shown that in CKD patients, increase in serum phosphate is due to reduction in secretion of phosphate by the renal tubules and this promotes secondary hyperparathyroidism with increased concentration of PTH¹⁰. It has also been explored that a progressive decline in GFR in CKD causes reduced levels of 1,25(OH)₂D. This prolonged CKD-associated hypocalcemia and hyperphosphatemia also drives the parathyroid gland for the secretion of more PTH to normalize the levels of PO₄ and Ca. This further explains the remarkably increased levels of PO₄ in the high PTH group¹¹.

Studies have shown that secondary hyperparathyroidism could lead to anemia by inhibiting the production of red blood cells, increasing the fragility and thereby causing fibrosis of bone marrow. Since, there exists positive correlation between FGF23 and PTH, it is believed that FGF23 could contribute towards the development of anemia in the dialysis patients. Therefore, we tried to establish correlation between various blood parameters and FGF23 but we did not find any correlation between any parameter associated with blood such as hemoglobin and FGF23¹². Similar results were obtained in the study conducted by¹³. In our study, we did not find significant difference in serum albumin levels of low and/or normal or high serum FGF-23 patients.

A strong positive correlation was found between the levels of FGF23 and PTH levels. Various previous studies have shown similar to our study a strong correlation between serum FGF23 levels and iPTH levels. FGF23 and PTH regulate each other mutually in a negative feedback loop. In this loop, PTH stimulates the production of FGF23 and FGF23 in turn lead to suppression of PTH synthesis⁴. Study by¹⁰ showed the activation of the nuclear receptor-associated protein-1 (Nurr1) is induced by PTH via the PTH receptor which further induces transcription of FGF23 in bone cells. A recent study aimed at demonstrating the correlation of FGF23 with various factors recruited 89 patients of CKD undergoing dialysis. The data obtained was in coherence to our study showing significant positive correlation between serum levels of FGF23 and PTH values⁵. However, various studies have shown contradictory findings to our study. It has been well established that FGF23 requires α Klotho as a co-receptor for binding to its FGFR receptor. Expression of α Klotho has been found on kidney, parathyroid glands and epithelium of the choroid plexus which limits the organs which can be targeted by FGF23. Parathyroid glands express both FGFR and α Klotho indicating correlation between

FGF23 and PTH. Contrary to our finding, some in vitro studies have shown that PTH mRNA expression and secretion of hormone is suppressed by FGF23². An in vivo study data concluded negative regulation of PTH secretion by FGF23⁹. Study by³ supported our finding. It showed that FGF23 null mice that were overexpressing FGF23 showed increased serum levels of PTH in spite of normal calcium, 1,25(OH)₂D, and hypophosphataemia supporting the fact that FGF23 induces production of PTH hormone¹⁴. A strong positive correlation was found between FGF23 and PTH in patient suffering from X-linked hypophosphataemia who are normocalcaemic and have low to normal 1,25(OH)₂D¹. Along with this, few studies wherein mice were overexpressing transgenic FGF23 caused secondary hyperparathyroidism. In¹⁴ showed in concordance to our finding that FGF23 is a long-term inducer of proliferation of parathyroid cell and secretion of PTH, thereby one of the cause for secondary hyperparathyroidism in CKD.

Levels of circulating FGF23 increase exponentially during early CKD and are enhanced upto 1000 folds in the case of kidney failure². These elevated levels of FGF23 are associated with all cause and cardiovascular mortality in the CKD patients⁵, dysfunction of LV, atrial fibrillation and cardiac hypertrophy development⁷.

These studies showing higher incidences of CVD in CKD patients along with the increase of FGF23 strongly recommend a strong correlation between CVD and levels of FGF23. This correlation could be established by conducting 2D- Echocardiography of the recruited CKD patients who were undergoing dialysis. Therefore, as another major objective of this study, we aimed at establishing a correlation between FGF23, LVH and LVEF. Our data suggested strong positive correlation of FGF23 with LVH. On the contrary, we found statistically significant negative correlation between FGF23 and LVEF. A study conducted by¹⁵ evaluated the relation between FGF23 and LVH in a cohort of elderly people consisting of 795 swedish men and women. Similar to our findings, it was found that there exists strong association between elevated levels of serum FGF23 and increased risk of LVH². In¹ conducted a cross-sectional study including 239 hemodialysis patients to establish the association between FGF23, LVH and LVEF. In concert to our findings, it was found that FGF23 was positively associated with LVH and negatively associated with LVEF. In⁸ showed that elevated levels of FGF23 were associated with LVH in a large, racially diverse cohort of people suffering from CKD. They further showed in mice model that FGF23 led to the pathological hypertrophy of the cardiomyocytes isolated from the rats. This was mediated through FGF receptor-dependent activation of the calcineurin-NFAT signaling pathway, independent of Klotho as injecting FGF23 in wild type mice resulted in LVH as well as klotho deficient mice resulted in increased FGF23 levels and LVH. In order to understand the mechanism by which FGF23 directly

regulates LVH, it was found that FGF23 directly induced the hypertrophic growth of cardiomyocytes and led to cardiac hypertrophy in in vivo mice model which was further abolished by the inhibition of calcineurin but not by the use of inhibitors against MAP kinase, PI3 Kinase or inhibitors of Akt². Later on FGFR4 was found to be the main molecule for effector function of FGF23 signalling in the heart which summarized that FGF23 induced cardiac hypertrophy is mediated by the FGFR4/PLCg/calcineurin pathway which activates NFAT and later on pro-hypertrophic NFAT target genes¹¹. Another mechanism behind FGF23 induced LVH was that pro-hypertrophic properties of FGF23 might be the direct regulator of Na-Cl channel NCC in the distal renal tubules by FGF23, thereby making it a sodium-conserving hormone.

Conclusions

This study conducted to evaluate the prognostic value of FGF23 indicated that along with determining the levels of iPTH in the patients undergoing hemodialysis, measurement of FGF23 could serve as strong prognostic marker. Higher levels of FGF23 in the patients of secondary hyperparathyroidism emphasize the need to decipher the FGF23-klotho axis in detail. This would provide more evidences and elucidation of novel therapeutic measures for treatment of secondary hyperparathyroidism. Moreover, linear correlation of FGF23 with LVH and left ventricular dysfunction strongly recommend to keep an check on cardiac parameters in dialysis patients with high FGF23 levels to avoid any mortality with CVD associated with CKD to the best possible level.

References

- Chen TK, Knicely DH, Grams ME. Chronic Kidney Disease Diagnosis and Management. *JAMA* [Internet]. 2019 Oct 1;322(13):1294.
- Lieske JC, Bondar O, Miller WG, Bachmann LM, Narva AS, Itoh Y, et al. A reference system for urinary albumin: current status. *Clin Chem Lab Med* [Internet]. 2013 Jan 1;51(5). Available from: <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/cclm-2012-0768/html>
- Ferrer, N. R., Romero, M. B., Ochendusko, S., Perpiñá, L. G., Malagón, S. P., Arbat, J. R., & Nodar, S. R. (2022). Solitary fibrous tumor of the thyroid. Report of a case with unusual clinical and morphological findings *Archivos de Patología*, 3(3), 104-109.
- Jadoul M, Albert JM, Akiba T, Akizawa T, Arab L, Bragg-Gresham JL, et al. Incidence and risk factors for hip or other bone fractures among hemodialysis patients in the Dialysis Outcomes and Practice Patterns Study. *Kidney Int* [Internet]. 2006 Oct;70(7):1358–66. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0085253815521273>
- Jamalpour, H., & Yaghoobi-Derab, J. (2022). A review of the philosophy of aesthetics and art based on theoretical and methodological considerations. *Revista de Investigaciones Universidad del Quindío*, 34(S2), 426-435.
- Donoso, P. C., Pérez, M. P. S., Aguirre, C. C., Barbosa, A. O., Gómez, C. M. G., Jimenez, A. M., & Nodar, S. R. Angiosarcoma suprarrenal primario. Reporte de caso. *Archivos de Patología*, 2022; 3(3), 96-103.
- Akaliin N, Okuturlar Y, Harmankaya Ö, Gedikbaşı A, Sezikli S, Koçak Yücel S. Prognostic Importance of Fibroblast Growth Factor-23 in Dialysis Patients. *Int J Nephrol* [Internet]. 2014;2014:1–6.
- Gutiérrez OM, Smith KT, Barchi-Chung A, Patel NM, Isakova T, Wolf M. (1-34) Parathyroid Hormone Infusion Acutely Lowers Fibroblast Growth Factor 23 Concentrations in Adult Volunteers. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol* [Internet]. 2012 Jan;7(1):139–45.
- Cardenas, C. A. (2023). Sarcomas:“A Comprehensive Review of Classification, Diagnosis, Treatment, and Psychosocial Aspects. *Clin Oncol Case Rep* 6, 6, 2.
- Clinkenbeard EL, Farrow EG, Summers LJ, Cass TA, Roberts JL, Bayt CA, et al. Neonatal Iron Deficiency Causes Abnormal Phosphate Metabolism by Elevating FGF23 in Normal and ADHR Mice. *J Bone Miner Res* [Internet]. 2014 Feb;29(2):361–9. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jbmr.2049>.
- Khorsandi, D., Zarepour, A., Rezazadeh, I., Ghomi, M., Ghanbari, R., Zarrabi, A., ... & Makvandi, P. (2022). Ionic liquid-based materials for electrochemical biosensing. *Clinical and Translational Discovery*, 2(3), e127.
- Mojahed, N., Mohammadkhani, M. A., Pourasgari, M., Rad, G. G. J., & Mohammadkhani, A. (2022). Viral Gastroenteritis Prevalence in Iranian Pediatric Population: A Systematic Review. *Avicenna Journal of Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 9(3), 124-129
- Zhang Q, Doucet M, Tomlinson RE, Han X, Quarles LD, Collins MT, et al. The hypoxia-inducible factor-1 α activates ectopic production of fibroblast growth factor 23 in tumor-induced osteomalacia. *Bone Res*. 2016;
- Cardenas CA. Glycolytic Enzyme Enolase-1 (ENO-1) as a Novel Target for Neuroendocrine-Like Prostate Cancer: A Review of Up-to-date Research and Future Prospects. *Clin Oncol Case Rep* 6. 2023;7:2.
- Aguirre C., The Perplexing Nature of Sarcomas Metastasizing to the Brain: Prognostic Patterns and Multidisciplinary Interventions, *Clinical Oncology: Case Reports*, 2023; 6(8), 1-4.